

**FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING FOR DEVELOPING
COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF LANGUAGE UNIVERSITY
STUDENTS**

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Annotation: The article deals with the role of foreign language in developing communicative competence of language university students, issues of communicative teaching of foreign language, communicative-oriented teaching, student-centered learning and extracurricular activities for learning foreign languages in light of post method era. It also discusses effective ways of learning a foreign language with some samples and research summaries by different Russian, English and Korean scholars.

Key words: communicative competence, student-oriented, monolingual, foreign language context, methods, communicative language teaching

The main goal of teaching a foreign language in a post method era is to develop students' communicative competence, which will help them to communicate in the language being studied in a natural environment. In this regard, it should be noted that the communicative approach is prevailing in teaching a foreign language taking into account many language aspects including intercultural level of communication.

Regarding views of the Russian scholars, the following strategic provisions are best known as characteristic of communicative teaching aimed at building ability to communicate in a foreign language, which are pointed out by E.I. Passov, who stated the following: the communicative orientation of teaching all types of speech activity and language means, stimulating the speech-cogitative activity of students, the

individualization of learning, on the functional organization of speech means, the situational organization of the learning process, the novelty, informativeness of educational material” [Passov, 2000: 10].

In order to confirm the importance and relevance of the communicative approach, R.P. Milrud and I.R. Maksimova specify that “work with students of different age groups requires taking into account the relevant didactic principles of accessibility, age and individual characteristics of students, consistency and systematicity in teaching, but the concept of communication retains its isomorphism at all age stages” [Milrud, Maksimova 2000: 9].

Many scholars state that among other features of the communicative approach to learning, which should be supplemented by these provisions, in which the focus is on the content and meaning of the statement, the speech context acquires special importance, literacy develops, fluency of the statement, literacy includes both the language form and the socio-cultural form. Adequacy of speech behavior, group forms of educational tasks are used and involuntary memorization is stimulated, the personal content of educational communication is encouraged.

The most important provision is the organization of student-oriented learning, on ensuring the moral and emotional intellectual development of students, on individual rates of language acquisition, on an integrated lesson with an abundance of interdisciplinary connections. Accordingly, communicative competence is formed, that is, the student's internal readiness and ability for foreign language speech communication. According to N.L. Bim, the implementation of a communicative approach is possible only taking into account the principle of student-centered learning, since “it is considered necessary to take into account the psychological factors of a communicative lesson, which include respect for the personality of the student, acceptance of the personal uniqueness of each participant in the work, protecting the individual from mental trauma in the lesson, preserving the personal autonomy of each trainee, the development of interpersonal relationships” [Bim, 2001:12].

V.V. Safonova notes that communicative tasks are inseparable from the stimulation of speech and thought activity in various ways, organizational forms and teaching methods. A foreign language in the context of communication-oriented learning becomes a means of socio-cultural education, forming the image of "themselves" among students as carriers of national culture [Safonova 2005: 107].

At the outset, it should be noted that the issues facing educators in implementing communicative language teaching (CLT) is not limited to the Native English teachers and non-native speaking teachers in the Korean context but similar monolingual EFL contexts. Those familiar with theoretical principles of CLT may already know that CLT emerged in the 1970's in the West. To review, the theoretical basis of CLT can be characterized as:

- ⇒ a focus on communication through interaction;
- ⇒ the use of authentic materials;
- ⇒ a focus on the learning process as well as the language itself;
- ⇒ belief that learners' own experiences can contribute to learning;
- ⇒ a linkage between language learning in the classroom and real-life activities (Nunan 1991 in Butler 2005 p. 424).

The work of the above researchers creates the basis for a deeper study of the main theoretical provisions of the communicatively oriented teaching of foreign languages. R.P. Milrud and I.R. Maksimova systematized the main conceptual provisions in their methodological literature: communicative-oriented teaching of foreign languages is possible in the conditions of an activity approach.

This principle is based on the theory of purposeful activity of the theory of speech activity, the authors of which are A.N. Leontiev, A.A. Leontiev, S.L. Rubinstein. Communicative teaching of foreign languages is of an activity nature, since verbal communication is carried out through "speech activity", which, in turn, serves to solve the problems of productive human activity in the conditions of "social interaction" of

communicating people. Participants in communication try to solve real and imaginary problems of joint activity with the help of a foreign language [Leontiev, 1997:59].

We consider that the activity essence of communicatively-oriented teaching of foreign languages is carried out through "activity tasks" (activities), which are implemented using methodological techniques (techniques) and create exercises (exercises).

Unfortunately, students with an orientation towards accuracy, form and structure may be unclear about the instructional objectives, learning process and means of evaluation, leading to confusion, frustration and alienation. Consequently, caution should be taken in curriculum and lesson development to ensure that tasks and materials are designed for the appropriate level and build on skills already developed. Since English language education in the Korean middle and high school system has long focused on vocabulary expansion, grammar and structure, students may demonstrate a strength and preference for form-focused instruction. By incorporating form focused tasks and activities into the communicative classroom students can apply traditional learning strategies and styles to produce meaning. For example, prior to engaging in an oral activity, instructors should review the basic vocabulary and grammatical expressions and allow students the opportunity to prepare notes before inviting oral responses. Subsequent written homework can reinforce the communicative language objectives of the lesson. [Kim, D.D. & Margolis, D. 2000]

According to our findings that the activity task is developed directly by the teacher and contains a communicative goal and a problem-cognitive task for students that they are trying to solve. The methodological technique contains a learning goal and a problem-methodical task for the teacher, which is to most effectively organize the student's activity and help him, in the course of solving the educational task, reach a cognitive result, that is, "learn activity".

Activity tasks for communication-oriented teaching of foreign languages are built on the basis of game, simulation and free communication.

In the methodological literature, tasks of the following types are distinguished:

- communication games
- communicative simulations in role-plays and problem-solving
- free communication (socialisation) [Safonova, 2005:107].

The activity essence of communicative-oriented teaching of foreign languages is realized in the position "here and now" ("here and now").

The "here and now" position:

- conditions are created for the speech-cognitive creativity of students;
- the process of foreign language speech thinking is carried out directly at the moment of development of the speech situation;
- foreign language communication is a spontaneous experience [Milrud & Maksimova, 2000:14].

However, there is one condition: the activity essence of communicatively-oriented teaching of foreign languages increases the importance of the methodical organization of the learning process (it's-the-process-that-matters). The fact is that communicative tasks are often performed in conditions of increased speech and physical activity of students, their free movement around the class and involuntary assimilation of educational material by them. Under these conditions, a carefully thought-out organization of communicative-cognitive activity in the form of a strictly defined training procedure is especially important. In our opinion, it is extracurricular activities that can create such conditions for learning.

According to E.I. Passov, the three-part form of performing communication-oriented tasks (three-phase framework) is currently becoming more widespread, which increases the efficiency of work. Almost any task can be performed:

The content of these stages varies depending on what type of work is used for learning in this lesson or in extracurricular activities: “text-based” or “task-based”, when, completing the task, students build own statements without relying on pre-given texts [Passov, 2000:93].

For example, in South Korea, many adults learn English as a foreign language for academic or workplace reasons (Park, 2011; Park, 2009). University students take private lessons in an effort to improve their English language skills so they become employed, and those who are already employed enroll in English classes to increase their chances at promotion (Choi, 2002; Park, 2009). The role of the English language in South Korea extends beyond college and the workplace and can be seen as playing a role in the globalization of Korea and the overall education system starting from elementary school, which both impact the adult Korean English learner’s experienced troubleshoot any breakdowns in communication that may arise (Rabab’ah, 2015; Kim, 2019).

We think that in the case of adult Korean English learners who are more likely to feel stress towards English due to a variety of factors and have been shown to have low levels of language proficiency, introducing several of the strategies can provide students with the tools needed to improve their communication skills. For example, educators can use authentic materials as a means for improving student motivation. Instructors should first take time to learn more about each student and the reasons for which they are learning English, and then use this information as a guide for developing lessons that relate more to students interests and goals.

It is also necessary to note the following advantage, the activity essence of communicative-oriented teaching of foreign languages by means of extracurricular work is realized in the conditions of a humanistic approach to learning.

As N.V. Baryshnikov, with this approach, positive conditions are created for the active and free development of the individual in activity. These conditions boil down to the following:

- ✓ students get the opportunity to freely express their thoughts and feelings in the process of communication;
- ✓ each participant in group communication remains the focus of attention of the others;
- ✓ self-expression of the individual becomes more important than the demonstration of language knowledge;
- ✓ even contradictory, paradoxical, even “wrong judgments” are encouraged, but they testify to the independence of students, their active position;
- ✓ individual violations of language rules (errors) and random errors (mistakes) are considered to be educational norms [Baryshnikov, 2002:30].

It should be noted that R.P. Milrud notes that speech errors in communication conditions are not only possible, but also normal. Conversational grammar (spoken grammar) allows certain deviations from the grammar of written speech. It contains elliptical constructions, one-part sentences without a subject, unfinished phrases, uncertainty and hesitation, reservations, etc. Features of colloquial grammar must be taken into account in the context of communication-oriented learning [Milrud, 2004: 14].

To form communicative competence outside the language environment, it is not enough to saturate the learning process with conditional communicative or communicative exercises that allow solving communicative tasks. It is important to give students the opportunity to think, to solve any problems that give rise to thought, to reason about possible ways to solve these problems, so that students focus on the content of their statement, so that thought is in the center of attention, and language acts only as a means of forming and expression of these thoughts. The process of teaching a foreign language in the implementation of forms of extracurricular work, built on a communicative basis, expands the possibility of the subject in solving this problem. Communicative learning is focused on the individual and is built in such a way that the direct activities of students, their experience, worldview, educational and

extracurricular interests and inclinations, their feelings do not remain outside the school threshold, but are taken into account when organizing extracurricular activities.

It must be remembered that training is based not only on the passage of educational topics, but primarily on the discussion of current life problems. At the same time, students get the opportunity to discuss current events in life, justify and defend their own opinions, learn the culture of communication, master speech etiquette, strategies and tactics of dialogic and group communication, learn to solve various communicative tasks, to be speech partners.

The purpose of teaching foreign languages in the first place is not a language system, but a foreign language speech activity, and not in itself, but as a means of intercultural interaction. Language is an element of culture that functions within a particular culture. Therefore, students must certainly be familiar with the characteristics of this culture. In this regard, the formation of students' sociocultural competence along with linguistic, linguistic and educational-cognitive competence at the level determined by the program of the state educational standard in foreign languages seems significant.

We are talking about the formation of socio-cultural language education in students both in the classroom and in extracurricular activities. In this case, the essence of sociocultural language education is reduced to the following provisions:

1. The path of language acquisition is a general educational process, the content of which is the culture of the country of the language being studied. Thus, foreign language culture is everything that is the source of foreign language cultural education in its four aspects: cognitive, developing, educational and educational.

2. In cognitive terms, the basis of education is the dialogue of cultures as a comparison of facts from the field of moral and aesthetic values, the way of life of native speakers.

3. In the educational plan, with a sociocultural approach, the emphasis is on identifying common moral guidelines in the life of the two peoples and the differences that exist between them.

4. The main task of the developmental aspect of extracurricular work in close connection with the lesson work is the formation of a strong motivation to study the language and foreign culture in dialogue with the native.

5. The educational goal of training in the considered approaches is reduced to the formation of communicative and sociocultural competence based on the native language of students.

Thus, the involvement of sociocultural components in teaching a foreign language in extracurricular activities is absolutely necessary to achieve the main practical goal - the formation of the ability to communicate in the target language. On this occasion, G.V. Kolshansky: "... the inclusion of country-specific elements, cultural information, realities, etc. in the program of teaching foreign languages. connected not with the desire to make the process entertaining, but with the internal necessity of the very process of teaching intercultural speech interaction in the language being studied" [Kolshansky, 1985:66].

In conclusion, we can mention that communicative learning in extracurricular work is built in such a way that all its content and organization are permeated with novelty, elements of entertainment, authenticity of the teaching materials used. Novelty prescribes the use of country-specific texts and exercises that contain something new for the student, the rejection of repeated reading of the same material. Thus, novelty ensures the rejection of arbitrary memorization (statements, dialogues, texts, etc.), develops speech production, the productivity of speech skills and arouses interest in the educational, cognitive activities of students.

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